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**METHODOLOGY FOR DEVELOPING AND ESTABLISHING A TARIFF FOR
LOADING RAILWAY CARRIAGES**

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Abstract: Shipment of reinforced concrete bridge structures to customers from manufacturers by rail is a favorable way of selling products. A significant part of the costs in this case is the cost of loading cargo onto platforms and wagons. To separately calculate the amount of the invoice for payment by its constituent elements, we have developed a method for establishing a tariff for rail loading.

Key words: Railway facilities, transport facilities, transportation, railway transport, cost of goods sold, loading costs, transportation costs, loading and unloading base, reinforced concrete bridge structures, transport services, overhead costs, profit rate, nomenclature, assortment, shipped products, tariff, loading schemes, loading method, material consumption rates, monetary valuations, other materials, props, turnstile.

Introduction

Loading of reinforced concrete bridge structures onto platforms and wagons requires significant expenses related to the maintenance of the PRB and loading and unloading operations. In addition, platforms must be equipped with turnstiles (a metal structure on a coupling of two platforms with special metal devices for fastening reinforced concrete beams of the superstructures of road bridges 24 m long. To transport beams on a coupling of two platforms, two identical turnstile supports with special devices for fastening the load are used).

For loading individual reinforced concrete products onto platforms and gondola cars, on the bridge, wooden beams and spacers of various sizes are required. *Therefore, wooden beams and spacers are produced at the loading site of reinforced concrete bridge structures, at the manufacturer.*

So, the process of loading bridge reinforced concrete structures is accompanied by a complex technology of production and assembly of container products, loading of cargo according to the approved scheme of loading of wagons, delivery of wagons by diesel locomotive for loading and for connection to the railway train at the departure station.

For accounting generalization of the processes of shipment of bridge reinforced concrete structures on sale also requires the organization of accounting of expenses by the composition of expenses and

calculation of the cost of railway loading and for repayment of these expenses by presenting invoices for payment to buyers, it is necessary to develop a tariff for their loading.

These issues are disclosed in the article.

Review of literature on the topic

Places of railway transport in the economy and the development of tariffs for the transportation of goods by scientists have been carried out many studies. In particular, according to: Jalolova M. Sh., "Railway transport is the basis of the modern economy. In this sense, it serves as an object of market relations, the effectiveness of its activities are interconnected with the activities and development of all sectors of the economy, enterprises and associations" [3].

According to certain groups of foreign scientists economists "the introduction of modern technologies of transport systems in Uzbekistan increases freight transportation by rail. Regulates transport systems, with optimization of free trade contracts and weight, and the size of vehicles leads to the implementation of unresolved problems in industry" [4].

Khaidarov I.A., studying the formation of tariffs for railway freight transportation and improving the implementation mechanism, concludes: "freight transportation tariffs, individual factors of goods sales complicate the activities of forwarders - intermediaries, especially residents. Many newly created intermediaries go bankrupt. The necessary conditions have not been created for the entry of small business entities, and small enterprises into the logistics services market" [5].

Based on the research of Shikhnazarova Zh. and Boboeva D., the following conclusion was made: "one of the ways to reduce transport services in the railway transportation of goods is the maximum use of the carrying capacity and capacity of wagons" [6].

Pluzhnikov K.I. and Chuntomova Yu. A. in the textbook "Transport Forwarding" examine a set of issues of the theory and practice of transport and forwarding and agency services - transport management. "Specific forms of transport and forwarding services for export-import and transit cargo, agency services for vehicles in international communications are disclosed. Much attention is paid to the transport and legal aspects of foreign trade contracts, international transportation agreements and terminal services" [9].

Research and results

At first glance, the process of shipping products in the cycle of financial and economic activity of enterprises is of little importance. When you delve deeply into the methods of cargo transportation, a number of questions arise related to their choice. Determining the amount of sales from the volume of shipment of products (works, services) is even more puzzling than a comprehensive study of this issue.

In the practice of economic entities, various methods of shipping products from manufacturers are distinguished:

- *pickup by buyers*, in which buyers with their own forwarder and motor transport goods from the sender's warehouse to the recipient's warehouse and bases.

In this case, the products are sold by manufacturers at the selling price of the goods, calculated taking into account the costs of warehouse storage of goods.

The costs of transporting the goods are formed by buyers and reflected in their balance sheet in the established order of accounting for procurement costs.

Centralized transportation of goods by road transport, in which manufacturers undertake the obligation to deliver goods to the warehouse and customer bases. In this case, a tripartite agreement is drawn up between the senders, recipients and the enterprises transporting the goods.

“Supplier” and (manufacturer) undertake the obligation to ship goods in the schedules and delivery volumes stipulated by the purchase and sale agreement drawn up between the buyers on the one hand, and "Buyers undertake to create the necessary conditions for the acceptance of goods from forwarding transport organizations and pay the amounts due to suppliers as the goods arrive, on the other hand.

Motor transport facilities are responsible for the integrity and damage of cargo during their forwarding between the bases (warehouses) of producers and buyers on the one hand, and producers are obliged to pay the amounts of payments due to transport organizations for the transportation of cargo by them, as soon as buyers confirm receipt of the cargo, in accordance with the contract of carriage, drawn up between transport organizations and shippers, on the other hand.

Thus, cargo transportation and settlement operations for the shipment of products are processed through manufacturers - centrally. According to this scheme of shipment and payment for goods and services, settlements between participants in cargo transportation are carried out in an optimal mode.

Cargo transportation from the supplier and to buyers is carried out in accordance with the concluded agreement between the supplier and the transport organization for the year. At the same time, there is no need to conclude agreements between buyers and transport companies for the transportation of goods, in each individual case of cargo transportation.

A significant portion of cargo is shipped by manufacturers via rail transport. The most optimal option for shipping goods via rail is also a centralized method of shipping cargo. That is, according to the obligation of manufacturers, railway companies deliver cargo to the station where its buyers receive it.

In this case, settlements between participants in centralized shipments are carried out by issuing invoices and payment documents on a contractual basis.

Transport organizations present invoices to producers for rendered railway services, and producers to buyers for shipped products. The payment amount includes: the cost of sold products, loading costs at loading and unloading bases and transportation of cargo via railways.

The most common way to cover cargo transportation costs from suppliers (manufacturers) is by presenting invoices for payment to buyers, on an invoice as a separate line item, such as “transport services” or “overhead costs”.

The amounts of payment for transportation expenses determined in this way will not justify themselves, for the following reasons:

- firstly, with the influence of the inflation process and changes in production technology, the ratio between the cost of sold products and the costs of their transportation to the buyer has the nature of constant change. The percentage ratios between the cost of goods and the costs of its transportation, with each change, are not recalculated;

- secondly, the relative calculation of the amount of expenses has an averaging nature of the distribution of costs by nomenclature and assortment of products. During the transportation of large-sized cargo, according to the loading scheme, it is necessary to equip wagons and platforms with special containers, sometimes expensive. For the shipment of each nomenclature and assortment of products, different containers are used, differing from each other in purpose, as well as the design of their manufacture. Although the containers used are of the same type in technical parameters of the structure, they can be distinguished by cost;

-thirdly, the number of the same containers used may be different, based on the method of loading the cargo. This means that the cost of the used container materials must also be taken into account in the context of each method of loading the cargo.

The above factors are a sufficient basis for the fact that when shipping products, the cost of the used containers must be taken into account in the context of each nomenclature and range of shipped products at the buyer and at the supplier.

Determining the costs of transporting cargo in the context of the nomenclature and range of shipped products is not of fundamental importance for the manufacturer, but in order to cover transportation costs, they must be taken into account in the context of buyers.

The correct methodological solution to this problem is the development and establishment of a tariff for rail cargo loading.

Using the example of calculating the tariff for rail loading of reinforced concrete bridge structures (RCBS), we will disclose this issue.

To disclose the indicators of RCBS shipment, we selected four products from among the shipped products, shipped using different loading schemes (Table № 1)

**Information on loading of reinforced concrete bridge structures
for December 20XX**

table №1

Loading number	Product name	Loading method	Loading of the product according to the standard for 1 wagon		Loading quantity (units)	Loading the product	
		Loading on (onto) the	quantity (units)	Weight (t)		quantity (units)	Weight (t)
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Balka B-4*140*120	platform	2	100,7	5	10	503,5
2	Plita P-9 K-7	platform	12	68,2	5	60	341,0
3	Plita P-9 K-7	platform	8	45,5	4	32	182
4	Blok 2 BDO-5*84	open wagons	19	64,7	5	95	323,5
	<i>Total</i>				19		1350,0

In the order of the loading scheme number, an invoice is issued for the shipped products and a technical report is made on the consumption of packaging materials for a given volume and composition of loading of bridge reinforced concrete structures. In this case, there are the following standards for the consumption of materials for railway loading.

Standard consumption of materials for railway loading

table №2

Loading number	Product name	Platform		Gondola car		Material consumption			
		quantity (units)	Weight (t)	quantity (units)	Weight (t)	requisites (m3)	Pad (m3)	Wire rod 6,5 (kilo)	Nail L-100 mm
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	Balka B-24*140*120	2	100,7	-	-	0,022	0,020	turnstile	
2	Plita P-9 K-7	12	68,2	-	-	0,1	0,1	165	0,71
3	Plita P-9 K-7	8	45,5	-	-	0,07	0,06	120	0,70
4	Blok 2 BDO-5*84	-	-	19	64,7	0,085	0,075	23,7	0,20

Based on the volume and composition of the bridge reinforced concrete structures loading and the “Standards for the consumption of materials for railway loading”, a report on the consumption of materials for railway loading is compiled.

**Report on the consumption of materials and goods
in December 20XX**

Table №3

Loading number	Product name	Number of Loads	Loading product		Material consumption for loading							
					requisites (m3)		Pad (m3)		Wire rod K-6,5 (kilo)		Nail L-100 (kilo)	
			quantity (units)	Weight (t)	According to the norm for 1 load	total	According to the norm for 1 load	total	According to the norm for 1 load	total	According to the norm for 1 load	total

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
1	Balka B-24*140*120	5	10	503,5	0,022	0,11	0,020	0,1	turnstile			
2	Plita P-9K-7	5	60	341,0	0,1	0,5	0,1	0,5	165	825	0,71	3,55
3	Plita P-9K-7	4	32	182,0	0,007	0,28	0,06	0,24	120	480	0,70	2,8
4	Blok 2BDO-5*84	5	95	323,5	0,085	0,425	0,075	0,375	23,7	118,5	0,20	1,0
	Total					1,315		1,215		1423,5		7,35

According to the presented table No. 3, the report on material consumption is compiled in the following order and calculations. The loading volume indicators in columns 1-5 are filled in accordance with and in the order of information on loading of reinforced concrete structures (table No. 5) and in columns 6, 8, 10 and 12, the material consumption rates are indicated in accordance with the data of table No. 2 “Material consumption rate for railway loading”.

By multiplying the number of loads (column 3) by the standard of material consumption (column – 6,8,10, 12), the quantity of the corresponding packaging materials used is determined. For example, for the 5th load of the P-9K-7 Plate according to loading scheme No. 2, the following requisites are used in the quantity of 0.5 m³ (5 * 0.1), the gasket in the quantity of 0.5 m³ (5 * 0.1), the K-6.5 rod in the quantity of 825 kg (5 * 165) and the L-100 mm nail 3.55 kg (5 * 0.71).

In this order and calculations, the amount of used packaging materials and other numbers of the loading scheme are determined. According to the summary data of the report, the following items were used for loading of bridge reinforced concrete structures: 1.315 m³ of props, 1.215 m³ of pad, 1423.5 kg of wire rod and 7.35 kg of nail.

To estimate the costs of loading operations in money terms, it is necessary to draw up a “railway loading rate” in accordance with the loading scheme for 1 wagon. The rail loading rate is determined based on the cost of the used packaging materials and other expenses of the “Loading and Unloading Base” (LUB).

The expenses of the loading and unloading base include the cost of fuel and other materials, basic and additional wages of the personnel of the loading and unloading base, deductions for social security, depreciation of fixed assets, the cost of electricity used and other expenses related to the sale of products.

The tariff for rail loading also takes into account the planned accumulation, i.e. the business income of the product sales structure.

Tariff for railway loading from December 1, 20XX (soums)

table №4

Loading number	Product name	Loading according to the norm for 1 wagon		Props according to price 725602-40	Pad according to price 726039-34	Wire rod by price 1801-253	nail L-100 at a price of 2485	Total graph 5-8	With other expenses 1,091	With planned accumulation 1,2
		units	tn	price	price	price	price			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
1	Balka B-24*140*120	2	100,7	15963	14521	turnstile	144074	174558	190443	228532
2	Plita P-9K-7	12	68,2	72560	72604	297207	1764	444135	484551	581461
3	Plita P-9K-7	8	45,5	50792	43562	216150	1740	312244	340658	408790
4	Blok 2BDO-5*84	19	64,7	61676	54453	42690	497	159316	173814	208577

According to table No. 4, the tariff for rail loading is calculated as follows:

For example, according to loading scheme No. 1 on beam B-24*140*120:

- cost of requisites = $0.022 * 725602.40 = 15963$

- cost of laying = $0.020 * 726039.34 = 14521$

The cost of the turnstile is determined based on the costs of maintaining the turnstile, per 1 load. The costs of maintaining the turnstile (6,771,450 soums) consist of the sum of rental payments for 2 railway platforms (3,811,450 soums) and repairs to the turnstile (2,960,000 soums). During the month, 47 loads were made with the turnstile. Based on the above data, the cost of using the turnstile for 1 load will be:

$$\text{Turnstile} = 6771450 : 47 = 144074 \text{ soums}$$

In total, direct costs are 174558 (15963 + 14521 + 144074) soums.

According to the calculation for the month, the costs of maintaining the PRB are 9.1% of the direct costs, i.e. the sum of all costs for loading scheme No. 1 is 190443 soums (174558 * 1.091) and taking into account the planned accumulation of 20% - 228532 (190443 * 1.2) soums. Thus, the tariff amounts for other items of the loading scheme for reinforced concrete bridge structures have been calculated.

According to the invoice, the supplier presents the buyer with an invoice for payment item by item:

- the cost of the shipped products, by nomenclature, quantity and prices for sale;
- the cost of railway services, by method, volume and tariff of transportation.
- the cost of railway loading, by quantity, loading scheme and tariff, which also includes the cost of packaging materials used during shipment of products.

Conclusions and suggestions

The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the strategy of actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. dated 07.02.2017 No. PQ - 4947 states: “further modernization and diversification of industry by transferring it to a qualitatively new level, aimed at the accelerated development of high-tech manufacturing industries, primarily in the production of finished products with high added value based on deep processing of local raw materials.

For this purpose, we have developed a methodology for setting tariffs for railway loading of reinforced concrete bridge structures on platforms and gondola cars, the technical and economic basis of which is:

- a scheme for loading reinforced concrete products on platforms and gondola cars;
- the rate of consumption of container materials according to loading schemes and types of reinforced concrete bridge structures;
- shop accounting of LUB costs and calculation of the cost of loading operations, etc.

Tariffing of railway shipments increases the efficiency of shipment of products for sale and settlements on arising obligations. It especially facilitates suppliers in determining the amount of payment on the invoice for shipment of products. It is recommended to calculate separately the cost of loading and transport services from the cost of products, in accordance with the established tariffs for loading cargo and accounting as part of the income of the main activity.

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